

THE EXPERIENCES AND PERFORMANCE OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY TEACHERS IN THE POST-PANDEMIC ERA: A CORRELATION

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The Experiences and Performance of Public Elementary Teachers in the Post-Pandemic Era: A Correlation

Lochelle T. Velos,* Rosalino T. Evangelio, Laarni T. Evangelio
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study investigates the experiences and performance of public elementary teachers in the post-pandemic era. Specifically, it examined their personal, professional, and social experiences and performance after the pandemic. This quantitative study used cluster sampling and was conducted face-to-face and online surveys with 105 teachers from New Bataan, Davao de Oro. Survey instruments were used to assess teachers' personal, professional, and social experiences, as well as their performance in the post-pandemic era. The findings reveal that teachers reported moderate agreement with their personal and professional experiences in the post-pandemic era, highlighting issues such as overcoming trauma, concerns about family health, and adjustments to lifestyle changes. However, there was no significant correlation between years of service and teachers' performance ratings, suggesting that tenure alone does not predict performance outcomes. Likewise, there was no significant relationship between teachers' experiences and their performance ratings during the post-pandemic era. The study recommends that students view post-pandemic as an opportunity and that teachers develop their teaching skills by integrating technology. Furthermore, they must support teachers' well-being, enhance teaching effectiveness, and foster a positive and supportive school environment in the post-pandemic educational setting, consider teachers with mental and emotional health, and prioritize teaching instructions that will help them face the post-pandemic challenges.

Keywords: *performance of teachers, personal experience, professional experience, public elementary teachers, experiences of teachers*

Introduction

Education is essential in making a better place and living in prosperity. Teachers go hand in hand in making education work, they are important aspects playing a big role in society by shaping the minds of students of different ages and serving as mentors, and facilitators of knowledge. However, with the unexpected pandemic that hits all over the world, schools have to shift to different learning methods adapting to the different instructions. Educators have to quickly adjust to deliver instructions effectively like digital platforms. The shift in delivery methods required resourcefulness, patience, creativity, and technological skill.

In developing countries, issues regarding school closure have been difficult for teachers, students, and parents. The lack of equipment, computers, and internet connection became a challenge in distance learning impacting the face-to-face education system of developing countries. However, during closures, teachers prepare teaching-learning strategies that suit post-pandemic. Developing countries emphasize the need to enhance teaching strategies in online and virtual design strategies to overcome the challenges brought by the pandemic (Tadesse & Muluye, 2020).

In the Philippines, COVID-19 affects the education system, financial resources, and mental health of teachers, students, and families. Especially, students and teachers are expected to use different platforms such as virtual and social media platforms to continue learning for accessibility despite the challenging situation and issues concerning the pandemic. These experiences highlight the existing problems and issues of poverty and inequality in the Philippines (Marquez et al., 2020).

In the New Bataan District, Division of Davao de Oro is one of those affected by the pandemic. Teachers who are both experienced and beginning teachers in this district struggle to adjust to the situation given that the pandemic is new to them. Teachers have difficulty adapting to the new learning platforms to deliver learning to the students. More so, teachers are facing immense challenges due to the fact that it can cost them life and is afraid to take risk. Aside from this, more teachers have lack of technological support, gadgets and proper training when it comes to virtual classroom, as many of them have a hard time in manipulating computers. This study aims to assess the experiences and performances of public elementary teachers in the New Bataan district in the post-pandemic era.

With this, the proponent came up with the idea of doing a comprehensive study of the experiences and performance of public elementary teachers in post-pandemic period if the variables have any relationship with each other. Teachers assigned in different local areas of New Bataan District to give us a clearer perspective on what are their experiences and performance during post-pandemic.

Research Questions

This study aimed to explore the experiences and performance of public elementary teachers in the post-pandemic era and how these experiences affect their teaching performance.

1. What is the profile of the teachers in the New Bataan District during the post-pandemic era in terms of their years of service?
2. What are the personal, professional, and social experiences of teachers in the New Bataan District during the post-pandemic era?

3. How are the performances of the teachers assessed during the post-pandemic era?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' years of service and their level of performance during the post-pandemic era?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' personal, professional, and social experiences and their level of performance during the post-pandemic era?
6. Is there a significant difference between the years of service and the experiences of teachers during the post-pandemic era?

Literature Review

Performance of Teachers

When it comes to the numerous reform initiatives aimed at ensuring high-quality education, it is thought that teachers' quality, efficacy, competence, and performance rank first. Regarding effectiveness, competency, and classroom management, there have been too many variables to take into account when evaluating teacher performance (Paz, 2021).

The pandemic has brought about significant transformations in both instructors and the educational environment, necessitating adaptations at every level of education. It has underscored the interconnectedness of global societies and the need for teachers to address prevailing social injustices. Teacher effectiveness directly influences students' learning outcomes, emphasizing the importance of qualified teachers (Witt, 2022).

The pandemic highlighted differences in access to education and worsened current inequities. Teachers will redouble their efforts to promote equity and inclusion, implement culturally responsive pedagogy, advocate for resources in underserved communities, and address systemic barriers to learning (Gay, 2018).

DepEd Elementary Teachers

DepEd oversees the recruitment and deployment of elementary teachers across the Philippines. These teachers are required to possess a bachelor's degree in elementary education or a related field, as well as a teaching license issued by the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC). They undergo continuous professional development programs to enhance their teaching skills and pedagogical knowledge (DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2015).

Experiences of Teachers

Teachers encountered numerous challenges in both the teaching-learning process and their personal lives. Nevertheless, collaborative efforts by teachers and managers led to an improvement in the quality of education over time. However, developing countries, including Iran, require strategic planning and foresight to effectively address similar crises and transition towards blended learning. (Goudarzi, et al. 2023).

González et. al. (2023) found that despite facing significant challenges, teachers experienced substantial learning opportunities during the COVID-19 pandemic. They diversified their use of digital technologies to facilitate content delivery and student interaction, introduced innovative approaches to course design and assessment, and fostered a greater sense of empathy towards students' circumstances.

Personal Experience

Individuals' experiences during the initial phases of the COVID-19 pandemic have not been universally positive or negative; rather, they have been highly diverse and notably complex. These findings emphasize the necessity of considering the multifaceted nature of individuals' responses to the pandemic in future endeavors to comprehensively assess the broad spectrum of COVID-19 experiences, which may incorporate elements from the domain of positive psychology (Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi 2000).

Professional Experience

Castroverde and Acala (2021) emphasized that educators developed learning modules for student utilization, highlighting that the transition in instructional methods presents challenges not only for students but also for teachers, who hold a vital role in the context of the new normal education. Agayon et al. (2022), noted that educators utilized personal coping strategies to address these challenges. Despite encountering such obstacles, the encouraging aspect is that they, as teachers, actively sought potential solutions to resolve the issues at hand.

Social Experience

Seifert (2020) stated that many social ties switched from traditional social networks to online ones. This was a lifesaver for many in terms of maintaining social ties, but for older folks who were on the receiving end of the technological gap, it could have led to even more social isolation. The fact that older adults who were already disadvantaged, socially isolated, or otherwise marginalized were more likely to experience the negative effects of the digital divide may have made their already severe levels of social isolation and loneliness even worse. This is regrettably one of the real tragedies of the pandemic's worsening, the digital divide. (Cosco et al., 2021).

Years of Service

Years are associated with teacher effectiveness founded on the creative idea that inexperienced teachers learn from experienced teachers, which is extremely appealing. Nevertheless, this comparison is not appropriate given that teaching is typically an independent profession where the majority of the teacher's learning is derived from reflective practice. Both action-based reflection and action-based reflection (Irvine, 2018).

Methodology

Respondents

The respondents were selected using cluster sampling, enabling the researcher to choose the respondents due to extensive size of the population. The public elementary school teachers from the five schools of Municipality of New Bataan who were actively teaching during the school year 2022-2023 were chosen as the respondents of the study. Specifically, the five schools were Cabinuangan Central Elementary School, Camanlangan Elementary School, San Roque Elementary School, La Purisima Elementary School, and Magangit Integrated School. Subsequently, the survey questionnaire was administered either online or offline, accommodating respondents' preferences and availability. The researcher provided a survey questionnaire about the experiences of the teacher's experiences and performance on post-pandemic period. The researcher practiced extreme caution by using open-ended questions.

Instruments

A validated researcher-made survey questionnaire was utilized for the quantitative data requirement. The study used a survey questionnaire as an instrument to determine the experiences of teachers on their personal, professional, and social experiences as well as their performance during the post-pandemic era. The survey questions consisted of 10-item questions for each of the following areas personal experience, professional experience, and social experience.

Procedure

The study commenced with the drafting of a formal request letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent of DepEd Davao de Oro, seeking approval for the research. Upon obtaining approval, the researcher acquired the necessary authorization and proceeded to correspond with the District Coordinating Principal in the New Bataan district. Following the acquisition of signatures, formal letters were sent to the school heads, formally apprising them of the study's objectives. Upon receipt of signed acknowledgment letters, arrangements were made to distribute and collect the survey questionnaires.

During the survey administration phase, a concise orientation session was conducted with the respondents to ensure their comprehension of the study's purpose and scope. First, the researcher presented the consent form to the respondents and let them freely sign the agreement. Second, the survey questionnaires were given to the respondents a few minutes after the orientation through online or face-to face. Upon conclusion of the designated survey period, collected questionnaires underwent compilation, tabulation, and rigorous statistical analysis.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical standards in research is important. This aim to protect the rights of the respondents and avoid misconduct. To secure the ethical research, a researcher should take responsibility and promote good research practice. Indeed researchers face an array of ethical requirements. The ethical principles involved in research are the beneficence and non-maleficence. Beneficence is the ethical principle of doing good while non-maleficence deals with doing no harm which may result from their research (Singh & Chauhan 2012).

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data, which were gathered through the research instrument of the study. It also provides statistical analysis and data interpretation to answer the problems of the study.

Table 1. *Profile of Teachers in terms of the Number of Years in Service*

<i>No. of Years</i>	<i>No. of Teachers</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
0-5 years	24	23%
6-10 years	34	32%
11-15 years	13	12%
16-20 years	8	7%
21-25 years	10	9%
More than 25 years	18	17%
Total	107	100%

Table 1 illustrates the number of respondents and the percentage distribution of teachers in the New Bataan District according to their number of years in service.

The Profile Experiences of the Teachers

Tables 2, 3, and 4 present the profile of the teachers in terms of the number of their personal experience, professional experience, and social experience. Each category was made up of ten survey questionnaires with their mean score obtained from the survey.

Table 2. *Profile of Teachers in terms of Personal Experience*

<i>Personal Experiences Questions</i>	<i>Mean</i>
1. I am still trying to overcome the trauma brought on by the pandemic	2.68
2. I feel conscious if someone in the family gets sick	3.34
3. I feel unsafe if I do not wear a face mask	2.75
4. I feel safe when I am at home	3.36
5. I feel uneasy when I get cold	3.07
6. I feel isolated	2.19
7. I feel that my lifestyle has changed	2.83
8. I learned to value time with my family	3.59
9. I refrained myself from going outside	2.64
10. I feel more relaxed and calm	3.06
Total	2.95

Table 2 shows the profile of teachers in terms of their personal experiences during the post-pandemic, as shown by their mean scores for each question. Based on the result, it can be concluded that the post-pandemic personal experiences among teachers involve emotional distress. With the mix of trauma, concerns for their health and safety, and changes in lifestyle activities. Nonetheless, they appreciate how important family time is for them. Although there are some negative indications like unease, isolation, and cautious behavior, hence there is also a good effect in the sense of flexibility, adaptability, and emotional well-being among teachers in the post-pandemic era. Thus, the personal experiences likely affected their overall well-being and communication with others.

Table 3. *Profile of Teachers in terms of Professional Experience*

<i>Professional Experiences Questions</i>	<i>Mean</i>
1. I feel stressed because the students' progress is slow	2.74
2. I feel mentally and physically exhausted	2.43
3. I feel the burdened as responsibilities are given to me	2.61
4. I feel unproductive because of the pandemic	2.31
5. I feel that my strategies are ineffective	2.05
6. I am still afraid of having a face to face instruction	2.45
7. I have a hard time trying to teach the students	3.11
8. I feel confident in teaching	2.93
9. I adapted easily to the situation	3.78
10. Teaching face-to-face is better than blended or modular learning	2.93
Total	2.73

Table 3 indicates the experiences of teachers as a professional during the post-pandemic period. From the result, it can be said that the post-pandemic experiences of teachers as professionals have made them feel stressed, exhausted, and challenged in delivering the lessons. However, they feel the need to be confident and adapt to the changes. Despite this fact, there is some uneasiness about returning to face-to-face instruction and concerns about teaching the learners effectively. Hence, teachers exhibit resilience and a willingness to adapt to the situation. Thus, it influences their effectiveness as teachers and their state based on the professional experiences they have during the post-pandemic period.

Table 4. *Profile of Teachers in terms of Social Experience*

<i>Social Experiences Questions</i>	<i>Mean</i>
1. I am still trying to adjust to going outside and not wearing a face mask.	2.52
2. I am still afraid of going outside	2.19
3. I do not feel safe when I encounter other people	2.36
4. I do not want to ride on public transportation	2.34
5. I do not like going to gatherings	2.32
6. I only attended family gatherings	2.64
7. I only went outside if necessary	2.65
8. I only communicate with my family	2.05
9. I lost communication with my friends	2
10. I feel socially deprived	2
Total	2.31

Table 4 indicates the results of a survey conducted among elementary teachers based on the social experiences they had in the post-pandemic. Based on the results gathered through the survey, it can be concluded that the post-pandemic social experiences of teachers affected them moderately. They feel the need to be cautious, fear being with other people, and are hesitant to attend any activities that involve interaction with others outside their immediate family circle.

It emphasizes the importance of prioritizing activities and maintaining communication mainly with family members, with some feelings of social deprivation and loss of connection with friends. These findings suggest that the pandemic has had a significant impact on teachers' social behaviors and experiences, leading to changes in their daily routines and social interactions. According to Rudert et al. (2022), the existing literature emphasizes the significance of individuals' social networks and the fulfillment of their needs, both in terms of personal well-being and their attitudes towards the pandemic and adherence to pandemic-related measures.

The Performance of Teachers

Table 5 presents the performance of the teachers based on their Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) rating in the school year 2022-2023.

Table 5. Performance of Teachers

IPCRF Rating	Adjective Rating	No. of Teachers	Mean
4.500-5.000	Outstanding	36	4.53
3.500-4.499	Very Satisfactory	71	3.96
Total		107	8.49

Table 5 shows the overall rating of the academic performance of teachers based on their IPCRF rating. It implies that the teachers undergoing evaluation have performed exceptionally well in their position or responsibilities and had met or exceeded the expected criteria. It shows that none of the teachers belonged to the adjective rating of satisfactory, unsatisfactory, and poor performance.

According to Llego (2014), the rating scale utilized in performance evaluation, specifically the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF), is grounded in the directives outlined in the Civil Service Commission Memorandum Circular No. 06 of 2012. This memorandum delineates the guidelines for establishing and executing the Strategic Performance Management System (SPMS) across all government agencies. The correlation between the rating scale and this memorandum underscores its fundamental role in shaping the framework.

Test Results of Null Hypotheses

HO1. The number of years in service of the teachers during the post-pandemic era is not significantly correlated with the teachers' performance.

Table 6. Relationship between Years of Service and IPCRF Rating

Factors	N	r	Interpretation	P	Tabular	Findings	Conclusion
Years in Service IPCRF Rating	107	0.163	Negligible correlation	0.094	0.05	Accept Ho1	No Significant Correlation

Table 6 illustrates the correlation between years of service and teachers' performance as indicated by their IPCRF ratings. The analysis reveals that there was no significant correlation between years of service and teachers' performance as assessed by their IPCRF ratings. The correlation coefficient, denoted by 'r = 0.163', indicates a minimal relationship between the ratings of teachers and their duration of service. Furthermore, the obtained p-value of 'p = 0.094', surpassing the conventional significance level of 'p = 0.05', leads to the acceptance of the null hypothesis (Ho1). This acceptance underscores that the duration of service in the post-pandemic period does not exhibit a significant correlation with the performance of teachers.

HO2. The experiences of the teachers are not significantly related to the teachers, performance during the post-pandemic era.

Table 7. Relationship between Average Experience and IPCRF Rating

Factors	N	r	Interpretation	p	Tabular	Findings	Conclusion
Average Experience IPCRF Rating	107	0.053	Negligible correlation	0.585	0.05	Accept Ho1	No Significant Correlation

Table 7 reveals the relationship between the teacher's experiences based on the average result of teacher experience with the teacher's performance during the post-pandemic era. The result showed that the r = 0.053 is a negligible correlation between ratings and average experiences of teachers. The Average experience was the average score garnered for personal, professional, and social experiences as answered by the teacher-respondents on the survey. The p = 0.585 is greater than p = 0.05 and thus we accept Ho2 which is the experiences of the teachers are not significantly related to the teachers, performance during the post-pandemic era hence, the experiences of the teachers are not significantly associated with the teacher's performances.

HO3. There is no significant difference between the number of years in service of the teachers and the teachers' experiences during the post-pandemic era in terms of their personal experiences, professional experiences, and social experiences.

There are two aspects to consider, each categorized accordingly: the duration of experience, ranging from 0 to 5 years, 6 to 10 years, 11 to 15 years, 16 to 20 years, 21 to 25 years, and more than 26 years; and the types of experiences teachers have, which include personal, professional, and social. Then, a Two-Factor Analysis of Variance (2-way ANOVA) will be used to analyze the data. Thus, the null hypothesis HO3 will be broken down into three sub-null hypotheses although the computations will be done only in one setting,

meaning, not separately for each hypothesis.

HO3.1 The number of years in service of the teachers has no significant effect during the post-pandemic era.

HO3.2. There is no significant difference between the levels of experience among teachers during the post-pandemic era.

HO3.3. There is no significant interaction between the number of years and the level of experience among teachers during the post-pandemic era.

Table 8. *Relationship between the Years in Service and Teacher's Experiences*

No. of Years	Label	N	x1	x2	x3	Total	X12	X22	X32	Total
0-5 yrs.	1	24	68.50	63.10	51.30	182.90	201.57	169.79	118.23	489.59
6-10 yrs.	2	34	101.60	91.60	76.70	269.90	308.04	249.76	180.73	738.53
11-15 yrs.	3	14	40.20	37.30	32.40	109.90	117.44	100.43	76.46	294.33
16-20 yrs.	4	7	21.10	19.40	17.40	57.90	63.93	54.22	43.70	161.85
21-25 yrs.	5	10	28.80	27.40	23.50	79.70	84.00	75.74	55.91	215.65
More than 25 yrs.	6	18	55.60	53.60	45.60	154.80	174.86	160.34	117.68	452.88
Total		107	315.80	292.40	246.90	855.10	949.84	810.28	592.71	2352.83

Table 8 shows the relationship between the years in service and the teacher's experience. The existing data on teachers' experiences were rearranged according to their categories as to the number of years. It shows the mean result of the teacher's experiences on their personal, professional, and social experiences. It indicates that the teacher's experiences differ from their personal, professional, and social experiences.

The analysis indicates that the number of years in service with the teachers does not influence their experiences in their personal, professional, and social aspects during the post-pandemic era. Furthermore, it does not have a substantial impact on teachers' experiences in the post-pandemic period. The findings indicate that the years of service of teachers do not affect their ability to adapt and navigate the challenges or changes arising from the post-pandemic environment.

Table 9. *Two-Way ANOVA*

Source of Variation	df	SS	MS	Computed F	Tabular F	Findings
Within	214	47.83	0.224			
Between	106			3.24	2.2141	Reject HO3.1
Factor 1	5	3.64	0.728	51.21	2.9957	Reject HO3.2
Factor 2	2	22.94	11.47	0.246	1.8307	Accept HO3.3
Interaction	10	0.55	0.055			

Based on the analysis HO3.1 rejects, indicating that teachers' number of years of service does not significantly affect the teachers how they viewed their roles during the post-pandemic period. Additionally, HO3.2 is being rejected, stating that there is indeed a significant difference in experience levels among teachers during the post-pandemic era.

Hence based on the findings HO3.3 accepts, stating that there is no significant interaction between the number of years and the level of experience among teachers during the post-pandemic. Thus it shows that there is no significant relationship between these variables during the post-pandemic era.

In conclusion, based on the results of the two-way ANOVA, it can be said that the number of years in service of the teachers has no significant effect as well as the interaction between the number of years and the level of experience among teachers during the post-pandemic era. However, there is a significant difference between the levels of experience among teachers during the post-pandemic era.

Conclusions

Teachers were expected to do their job even in times of pandemic. Teaching is crucial not just for teachers but also for the students for their learning outcomes. The pandemic making it more difficult for teachers to deliver their instructions shifting to blended learning. It affects teachers' performance since they have to adapt to the fast-changing educational environment.

However, the results indicated that the number of years in service of teachers did not correlate significantly with teacher performance during the post-pandemic period. The study found no significant correlation between years of service and teacher performance, indicating that both new and experienced teachers faced similar challenges and demonstrated comparable performance levels during the post-pandemic period. At the same time, there is no relationship between teachers' experiences about their personal, professional, and social experiences with the performance ratings during the post-pandemic era. Overall, based on the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) ratings of teachers as assessed most teachers were generally positive, being in the categories of "Outstanding" and "Very Satisfactory."

The Pandemic greatly affected various industries, such as the changes of work stations, employment, career paths to be taken, and business financial situations which also affected the teachers. Teachers' personal, professional, and social experiences were significantly

impacted by the pandemic. Teachers reported significant emotional distress and a need for better mental health support, highlighting the importance of providing resources for emotional and psychological well-being. As teachers continue to do their job despite the difficulty and the situation they were facing during the post-pandemic period, they are expected to do their job and prioritize the student's education. Some of the teachers were adept at the changes however, there were still teachers who had difficulty with the changes such as being digitally inclined. They feel pressured and left behind by the trends using the new platforms and they feel doubtful and conscious about returning to face-to-face instruction which add to their stress and problems on the situation they were in.

Even after the pandemic, the experience of teachers was considerably impacted by the issues and concerns on the student's development regarding their academic performance and academic progress. The need for seminars and training is needed to effectively teach and resolve the issues faced in the post-pandemic period (Amar et. al., 2024). Navigating the difficulties of the post-pandemic teaching landscape became contingent upon the exchange of experiences, resources, and best practices. The experiences of teachers can differ across various domains, including their personal, professional, and social experiences. Understanding and addressing the dynamics within each domain contribute to the overall well-being and effectiveness of educators in their roles.

Students must learn to understand the situation and support teachers in facing the circumstances to attain the goals together. Considering the workloads and the challenges that teachers were facing after the pandemic they have to implement self-care strategies to manage stress and exhaustion of the teachers such as maintaining a healthy work-life balance. Parents must help teachers and cooperate by encouraging children to study and perform as needed. School administrators should provide a positive and supportive community with the teachers where they feel valued, respected, and empowered to face the challenges. They must invest in resources and infrastructure to ease the transition to blended learning instructions and to address any gaps in technology improving teachers' knowledge of technology and training among teachers, especially during post-pandemic.

It can be said that though teachers are greatly impacted and challenged during the post-pandemic period, they still manage to adjust and cope with the situations demonstrated professionally. The study highlights the teacher's adaptability and resilience during the post-pandemic era, giving importance of teacher's emotional support, professional development and integrating new teaching methods. Teachers' commitment is needed for continuous professional growth and development to maintain high performance levels.

Hence, it needs further research based on the results gathered from the study and the impact of the pandemic on teachers' well-being, performance, and professional development. Explore more on the factors that may influence the experiences and performance of teacher's post-pandemic period.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Lochelle T. Velos

Assumption College of Nabunturan – Philippines

Engr. Rosalino T. Evangelio

Assumption College of Nabunturan – Philippines

Laarni T. Evangelio, Ed.D

Assumption College of Nabunturan – Philippines